

Factors Influencing Surgical Site Infections in Abdominal Surgeries: A Cross - Sectional Analysis

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Abstract:

Background: Surgical Site Infections (SSIs) increase healthcare costs, hospital stays, and morbidity. This study examines the reasons for SSIs after abdominal surgery in low- and middle-income nations like India, where inadequate medical infrastructure makes them more common.

Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted at Pawapuri Nalanda, Bihar's Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Science from August 2023 to August 2024. The study involved 150 abdominal surgery patients. Medical records were used to collect demographics, operation details, co-morbidities, and postoperative factors. According to CDC guidelines, SSI incidence was evaluated, and multivariate logistic regression showed significant risk factors.

Results: Diabetes (38%), obesity (35%), and surgeries over three hours (28%), had the greatest incidences of SSIs at 21.3% of 150 patients. Risk factors for SSIs include obesity (OR 2.8, $p < 0.01$), diabetes (OR 3.1, $p < 0.01$), and longer surgery time (OR 2.4, $p < 0.01$). Patients who received prophylactic antibiotics within 60 minutes after surgery had 13% fewer SSIs than those who received them later (29%).

Conclusion: Long operational time, obesity and diabetes increase abdominal SSI risk. Prophylactic antibiotics must be given quickly to reduce infection rates. These findings emphasise the significance of specialised therapy to improve surgical outcomes.

Keywords: Abdominal surgeries, Diabetes, Obesity, Prophylactic antibiotics, surgical site infections.

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Introduction

Surgical Site Infections (SSIs) in postoperative sequelae affect patient well-being, healthcare costs, and death and disability [1]. Surgical site infections occur within a month of surgery. Deep infections impact organs and tissues, while superficial infections affect the skin [2]. Extended hospital stays, readmissions, and potentially fatal infections like sepsis are connected to SSIs, which the WHO considers a major public health issue [3].

SSIs are more likely in abdominal surgeries due to contamination, intestinal bacteria, and internal organ involvement [4]. After abdominal surgery, infections can impede wound healing, cause organ failure, and kill. Low- and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs) like India have higher SSIs due to a lack of standardised infection control, preoperative care, resources, and healthcare infrastructure [5].

Significance of SSIs in Abdominal Surgeries in Developing Regions:

Developing regions like Bihar, India, have a high rate of surgery site infections due to inadequate healthcare, lack of contemporary surgical therapy, and poor sanitation and cleanliness. Due to hospital overpopulation and poor sterilisation, surgical infections are frequent. Malnutrition, diabetes, obesity, and inadequate antibiotic treatment during surgery promote surgical site infections. Abdominal surgeries are more likely to induce infection due to their intricacy.

The large range of gastrointestinal system germs can swiftly spread and cause infections if the surgical incision is not adequately closed. Lack of finance, resources, and competent surgical professionals on surgical teams makes SSIs more common in developing nations.

Figure 1:

Risk Factors for SSIs: [6,7] have examined abdominal SSIs causes. These include patient characteristics like age and immunological state and systemic factors like long operating times or emergency surgeries, poor antibiotic use, pre-existing diseases, and other medical issues. According to [8,9], insufficient sterilisation and delayed wound closure jeopardise elective and

emergency abdominal surgery. [10] Suggests India's healthcare system needs better infection prevention and control.

This is especially true in rural and urban underdeveloped areas. Urban SSIs have decreased due to better cleanliness and antibiotic regimes, but rural areas like Bihar continue to have higher infection rates due to a lack of resources [11].

Figure 2: Surgical Site Infection (Source: [12])

Rationale of the Study: The medical community must prioritise this work since SSIs affect patient outcomes and healthcare systems. Understanding the risk factors for abdominal SSIs can help doctors reduce infection rates. Identifying and controlling surgical site infection variables improves postoperative outcomes, healthcare costs, and

patient safety. In Bihar, where healthcare institutions face restrictions, this is crucial. This study's unique data can improve infection control and resource allocation.

Objectives

- To identify the factors influencing surgical site infections in abdominal surgeries.
- To provide recommendations for reducing the incidence of SSIs based on the identified risk factors and outcomes.
- This study aims to contribute valuable insights into the prevention and management of SSIs in the region, ultimately improving patient care and reducing postoperative complications.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: Cross-sectional study data was collected at the Bhagwan Mahabir Institute of Medical Science in Pawapuri Nalanda, Bihar, from August 2023 to August 2024. The goal of this study was to determine risk factors for abdominal SSIs. This study recorded the study population's infection rates and risk variables throughout time. Cross-sectional analysis was done to identify patient, surgical, and postoperative characteristics associated with SSI.

Sample Size and Population: The study included a total of 150 patients who underwent various abdominal surgeries at Bhagwan Mahabir Institute of Medical Science during the study period. The sample size was determined based on the availability of patients meeting the inclusion criteria, with a focus on ensuring sufficient representation of different demographic groups and types of surgeries. The patients' medical records were reviewed to gather relevant data regarding their surgical procedures and outcomes.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients of all ages.
- Underwent abdominal surgery (both elective and emergency) at the institute between August 2023 and August 2024.
- Surgical procedures included: Appendectomies, Cholecystectomies, Hernia repairs, Bowel resections
- Completed the entire postoperative follow-up period.
- Medical records contained complete data.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with pre-existing infections (systemic or localized to the surgical site).
- Patients with compromised immune systems, including: HIV-positive individuals, Long-term corticosteroid users, Patients undergoing chemotherapy

- Incomplete medical records.
- Patients transferred from other facilities for postoperative care.

Data Collection

A retrospective review of all eligible patients' medical records was used to collect data. A typical data collection form retrieved relevant data on many factors. Demographic data included age, gender, BMI, and smoking status.

The surgical record included the surgery's purpose (elective or emergency), operations, time, antibiotic use, and anaesthesia. Diabetes, high blood pressure, obesity, and heart disease were also found. Postoperative hygiene, wound care, and drain or surgical aid use were assessed. Postoperative infection management and prophylactic antibiotic times and types were also recorded. Using CDC criteria, we thoroughly evaluated each patient's medical record to identify SSIs. Infection symptoms include redness, swelling, discharge, fever, and the need for medications or surgery confirmed the diagnosis.

Statistical Analysis: Data was entered into statistical software for analysis. Descriptive statistics were used to summarise gender, age, comorbidities, surgical procedures, and infection rates. For categorical data, we used percentages and frequencies; for continuous variables, means and standard deviations.

To identify SSI-affecting variables, multivariate logistic regression analysis was employed. Independent variables included population characteristics, co-morbidities, surgery, length of stay, and antibiotic prophylaxis. Outcome variable was SSI presence. Odds ratios (ORs) with 95% CIs were calculated to assess variable correlations. All analyses were statistically significant when $p < 0.05$. This study investigated abdominal surgery-related SSIs using statistical methods. This should aid preventive and improve patient well-being.

Results

Patient Demographics: The study included 150 Bhagwan Mahabir Institute of Medical Science abdominal surgery patients from August 2023 to August 2024. The mean age was forty-two and a half, but patients ranged from 18 to 75. A gender balance was achieved with 85 male (56.7%) and 65 female (43.3%) patients. Nearly half of patients had numerous health issues, notably diabetes (28%) and obesity (22%). Patients reported 18% hypertension and 15% habitual smoking.

Table 1: Patient Demographics

Parameter	Value
Total Patients	150
Age Range	18 - 75 years
Mean Age	42.6 years
Gender Distribution	
Male	85 (56.7%)
Female	65 (43.3%)
Patients with Comorbidities	45%
Most Common Comorbidities	
Diabetes	28%
Obesity	22%
Hypertension	18%
Active Smokers	15%

Prevalence of SSIs: After surgery, 32 (21.3%) of 150 patients developed SSIs. Diabetics, obese patients, and long-term surgery patients experienced more surgical site infections. Infections commonly caused wound drainage, redness, oedema, fever, and discomfort within two weeks of surgery.

Table 2 Prevalence of SSIs

Category	Patients with SSIs (n=32)	Percentage
Total patients	150	100%
Patients with SSIs	32	21.3%

Figure 3:

Figure 4:

Surgical Factors: Elective and emergency abdominal operations were performed. Hernia repairs (18%), intestinal resections (12%), appendectomies (30%), and cholecystectomies (20%) were the most prevalent procedures. About 60% of surgeries were elective and 40% were emergency. Elective procedures (17%) had a far higher SSI risk than emergency surgeries (27%).

Operation duration affected infection rates. Surgery site infections (SSIs) were 28% for procedures over 3 hours and 15% for shorter ones. Extended surgical exposure destroys tissue integrity and increases contamination, which may explain this correlation.

Table 3: Surgical Factors

Surgical Duration	Patients (n=150)	SSI Rate
< 3 hours	90	15%
> 3 hours	60	28%

Risk Factors

Several risk factors can cause surgical site infections (SSIs). The study's obese population (22%; BMI >30) had a 35% SSI rate compared to 16% for non-obese people. The difference is that obese patients have more subcutaneous tissue, which makes wound healing harder and increases infection risk. Of 42 diabetics, 16 (38%), got SSIs; 11% of non-diabetics had infections. This reinforces the concept that diabetes is a substantial risk factor. Diabetes is known to impair wound

healing and immune function. Smoking limits tissue oxygenation and wound healing, increasing the risk of infection. 15% of smokers had a 30% SSI rate, compared to 18% of non-smokers.

Surgery length also affected infection rates: SSI rates were 15% lower for surgeries under three hours and 28% higher for those over three hours. Antibiotics given within 60 minutes of the incision had a 13% SSI risk, compared to 29% for those given later. Prophylactic antibiotic timing and administration prevented SSIs.

Figure 5:

Figure 6:

Table 4: Risk Factors

Risk Factor	Percentage of Patients with the Risk Factor	SSI Rate Among Patients with the Risk Factor	SSI Rate Among Patients without the Risk Factor
Obesity (BMI >30)	22%	35%	16%
Diabetes	28%	38%	11%
Smoking	15%	30%	18%
Surgical Duration >3 hrs	40%	28%	15%
Prophylactic Antibiotic Use	100% (all patients)	13% (administered within 60 minutes)	29% (administered outside the recommended window)

Figure 6:

Statistical Findings

A multivariate logistic regression analysis was conducted to identify the most significant risk factors for SSIs. The analysis revealed that prolonged surgical duration (OR 2.4, 95% CI 1.3–4.2, $p < 0.01$), obesity (OR 2.8, 95% CI 1.5–5.0, $p < 0.01$), and diabetes (OR 3.1, 95% CI 1.7–5.6, $p < 0.01$) were the strongest independent predictors of SSIs. Smoking was also a significant factor, though to a lesser extent (OR 1.9, 95% CI 1.1–3.3, $p = 0.04$).

Discussion

This study found several key factors that highly predict abdominal SSIs. Long operation duration, diabetes, obesity, and inappropriate prophylactic antibiotic therapy were the biggest risk factors. These findings support previous research on abdominal SSIs and risk variables.

The most significant conclusion was that extended operating periods increased surgical site infections. More infections occurred with surgeries over three

hours, maybe because more interior tissues were exposed and contamination was more likely. Previous study has linked longer surgical procedures to an increased risk of SSIs, possibly because to germ exposure of the surgical incision.

Comorbidities like diabetes and obesity also affected SSI risk. Due to their compromised immune systems and slower wound healing, diabetics are more susceptible to infection. Because obese persons have greater subcutaneous tissue, it's difficult to access the operation site and heal the wound, SSIs are more likely. Our results support earlier research that shows these comorbidities enhance postoperative infection risk. Avoiding infections required timing and dosage of prophylactic medications. Patients with delayed or poor antibiotic therapy had more SSIs. This follows CDC and WHO recommendations to deliver antibiotics immediately, preferably one hour before incision, to prevent infections.

Comparison with Existing Literature

Table 5: Comparison Table

Study	Study Type	Sample Size	Findings
Present Study	Cross-sectional	150	SSIs incidence was 21.3%. Major risk factors included prolonged surgery (>3 hours), diabetes, obesity, smoking, and delayed prophylactic antibiotics.
Study 1 [13]	Cross-sectional	300	SSIs incidence was 26%. Significant risk factors were poor hygiene practices, lack of proper antibiotic prophylaxis, and longer hospital stays.
Study 2 [14]	Multicenter cohort	183 hospitals	SSIs were the most common healthcare-associated infection (HAI) in surgeries. Prolonged surgery and improper antibiotic timing were major contributors.
Study 3 [15]	Systematic review	2200 (multiple)	Globally, SSIs accounted for 11.8% of infections in low- and middle-income countries. Key risk factors included obesity, diabetes, and surgical duration.

The table compares three abdominal surgery SSI studies to the current study. This study identified 21.3% SSIs, similar to Study 1's 26%. Both trials found that extended surgery and poor prophylactic antibiotic treatment increased SSI risk. Study 2 examined SSIs as a common infection in healthcare settings, emphasising surgical factors; Study 3 reviewed the literature and found that 11.8% of infections in low- and middle-income countries were SSIs, highlighting the prevalence of diabetes and obesity. The findings emphasise the need to reduce SSIs and recognise crucial risk factors in all scenarios.

Limitations

This study has pros and cons. An initial sample size of 150 patients may not represent the local abdominal surgery community. Stronger data from a larger sample allows for broader inferences. Because the study used prior patient data, bias or insufficient data collection may occur. Another downside is that clinical symptoms alone can overlook certain individuals, especially those with subclinical infections that were not treated or reported in medical records. The study did not examine whether surgeon techniques affect infection rates.

Suggestions for Future Research

Future research should examine additional characteristics that may affect abdominal SSIs and address the study's limitations. The effectiveness of preoperative antibiotics in avoiding infections in high-risk patients like diabetics and obese people needs further study. Future studies should examine wound care and how different wound closure approaches may reduce SSIs. This study didn't account for anaesthetic procedures or postoperative care regimens; larger samples could provide additional data. Longitudinal research may assist explain how SSIs affect patients' outcomes and recovery.

The study illuminates key characteristics that affect abdominal SSIs and provides clinical practice recommendations for similar healthcare settings. Targeted actions based on these findings can enhance patient outcomes and reduce SSIs.

Conclusion

In this study, long surgical durations, comorbidities like diabetes and obesity, and inadequate preventative antibiotic therapy contributed to abdominal Surgical Site Infections (SSIs). Our findings emphasise the importance of timely preoperative therapy, antibiotic regimen adherence, and successful surgical methods to minimise SSIs. Perioperative management and infection control standardisation can considerably lower infection rates and increase patient safety. SSIs affect healthcare systems and patient outcomes, making this crucial. Future research should examine effective antibiotic regimens and wound care strategies to reduce SSIs and improve surgical outcomes.

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